

HUMAN-IN-THE-LOOP FRAMEWORK FOR UAV-UGV COORDINATED ONSITE INSPECTION OF PRECAST BRIDGE CONSTRUCTION

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Abstract:

This project developed a novel human-in-the-loop UAV-UGV coordination framework for on-site quality inspection of precast bridge construction. In the proposed framework, UAV provides global coverage for inspectors to quickly identify the components and construction activities for inspection while UGV navigates to specific locations for close inspection following human guidance. A new gaze-directed human-machine interface was developed, where inspectors can express their guidance via natural gaze movements to reduce worker mental load. A prototype was developed to integrate the entire framework, and the system was tested in both simulation and real-world controlled environments. The developed system offers a unified remote operator interface for gaze-based multirobot coordination. Through the use of intuitive gaze movements, our research project aims to reduce worker mental load, make inspection tasks accessible to a wider range of operators, allowing data to be rapidly captured and stored for documentation and verification purposes, and to increase single operator productivity by making remote operation more accessible and intuitive. The proposed framework is expected to transform the practice of onsite quality inspection for precast infrastructure construction by establishing intuitive multi-robot-human teaming for efficient inspection. Such a system can be extended to provide guidance during bridge installation, thus improving construction quality and durability with reduced rework. The proposed framework can also be extended for lifecycle inspection, including offsite component inspection and condition monitoring of existing infrastructure, and eventually improve the durability and extend the life of precast transportation infrastructure.

1. INTRODUCTION

Precast bridge components such as girders, decks, and columns facilitate accelerated bridge construction while offering improved construction quality due to the high quality control standards at the offsite precast plants. In the offsite precast plants, components need to go through rigorous dimensional and surface quality inspection, after which they are transported to the jobsite for final assembly (Ma et al. 2023). Contrastively, onsite quality inspection, which still largely relies on manual visual inspection on limited samples, is yet to match up with the standards of the offsite practices (Leea et al. 2020). Onsite quality inspection for precast bridge construction is crucial due to potential defects after the offsite construction phase. For example, damage and defects may occur during the component transportation process. The quality of onsite construction activities such as connection joint sealing, post-poured wet joints, and component localization and alignment, also significantly affect the overall structural integrity and durability. Many sensing systems, such as laser scanning (Liu et al. 2018) and vision-based systems (Luo et al. 2021) are developed for quality inspection of precast components.

Despite the advances in data processing and analysis tools, current quality inspection of precast components typically requires inspectors' visual check or data collection by carrying devices (e.g., 3D laser scanners) to different locations (Ma et al. 2023), which is very time-consuming, error-prone, and labor-intensive. Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have enjoyed increased adoption in infrastructure inspection (Seo et al. 2018a; b) given their advantages in rapid and large spatial coverage and the ability to reach inaccessible areas from the air. However, for UAVs alone, accessing ground activities is still difficult and unsafe when it is too close to work activities, coupled with limited payload. On the other hand, unmanned ground vehicles (UGVs) can carry larger payloads, hence better sensors, and operate for extended periods with better access to ground-level workspaces. However, UGVs usually have less field of view and lower coverage speed compared to UAVs (Asadi et al. 2020). Therefore, UAV-UGV coordinated systems are promising solutions with emerging applications in construction (Asadi et al. 2020; Elmakis et al. 2022), space exploration and mapping (Qin et al. 2019), etc. Despite the great potential, two limitations persist. First, UAV and UGV are often required to move in proximity for mutual localization. Second, extensive human expertise and experience are still required, e.g., to determine the optimal route and/or find the optimal inspection location. In addition, the control of multiple robots typically relies on multiple controller devices, which may increase the human mental load and risk of error.

This project aims to develop a novel human-in-the-loop UAV-UGV coordination framework for on-site quality inspection of precast bridge construction. Our framework incorporates the unique strengths of aerial and ground robots in order to automate the inspection process. We proposed gaze as a primary interfacing means to broaden the accessibility of the interfacing system, allow operators to use their hands for other control interfaces such as mouse or keyboard, and reduce user mental workload on the operator.

2. METHODOLOGY

Figure 1 illustrates the overview of the framework. First, a hierarchical framework was developed to enable a UGV to automatically locate and navigate to the inspection area as indicated by the UAV, leveraging sensing data from the onboard GPS and camera of both robots. Then, a gaze-directed and AI-powered human-robot interface (HRI) was developed such that the robot could navigate to a specific location based on human gaze and gaze fixations. Finally, a prototype was developed with all system integrated, and was tested in real-world settings.

2.1 UAV-UGV Coordinated Localization and Navigation

A common way of handling multi-robot coordinated navigation is through GPS-based navigation. Once a GPS point is reached by a ground robot, further methods are needed by the UGV in order to verify that it is in the correct location and to determine which target it should be inspecting. We incorporate these ideas into our framework by allowing a drone operator to gather aerial reference image with a drone and then set GPS-based waypoints to the object which a UGV can then navigate to. The reference images capture the

inspection target and any contextual details such as surrounding landmarks that can later be used for target identification by the ground robot. Figure 2 provides a system architecture of the GPS-based navigation

Figure 1. Gaze-directed UAV-UGV coordination framework for onsite quality inspection.

Figure 2. Gaze-directed UAV-UGV coordination framework for onsite quality inspection.

Once the target point is reached, the UGV faces the challenging task of identifying the target in a scene. Construction sites are very dynamic with the interactions between equipment, materials, and workers so it is unlikely that the scene in a reference image captured by a drone would then completely correspond with the scene the ground robot finds at a later time. In addition, the perspective of the drone to the target object may not align with the perspective of the ground robot to the target, thus some homography transformation would be required to align the different perspectives. For these two challenges, we implement a recent visual correspondence model, XFeat (Potje et al. 2024), which uses a lightweight Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture that achieves fast and accurate visual correspondence.

2.2 Gaze-directed Human-Robot Interface

Once the UGV navigates to the inspection area, a gaze-directed human-robot interface was developed to allow inspector to guide the robot to the special object to inspect via natural gaze movement. Integrated with a mobile eye tracker, i.e., Pupil Core eye tracking glasses in our study, this interface enables an operator at a control station to remotely direct UGV at a construction site toward a specific object of interest by simply adjusting their line of sight on video streams from UGV. Given the coordinates of the remote operator's gaze relative to the world view of the Pupil glasses, an image frame captured from the world video stream of the Pupil glasses can be segmented at the coordinate to isolate an object of interest. The user has the flexibility to start the segmentation over as required. When a suitable target has been isolated, it is then sent to the UGV to localize the target in its scene leveraging depth information obtained from an onboard sensor. The UGV would then autonomously navigate to the target and gather a collection of images

of the structure. The collected dataset is then streamed back to the control station for further inspection and data processing. Figure 3 presents a visualization of the proposed interface.

Figure 3. System diagram for gaze-based human-robot interface.

2.3 System Integration and Interface Design

The final task involved the integration of the previous two tasks into a unified framework. For this portion of the project, we moved the application to browser based and incorporated docker for the application building, which allowed us to quickly deploy the application on more devices and operating systems. The system diagram in Figure 4 shows how the interface centralizes inputs from the drone and ground robot to facilitate the coordinated on-site inspection. The task sequence is detailed in Section 3.

Figure 4. System diagram for multi-robot collaborative inspection mission.

3. IMPLEMENTATION

The final prototype and experiment of our project involved field testing of our framework in an outdoor environment for the inspection of a target object. We used a Clearpath A200 robot as the UGV and a DJI M30T as the drone. We conducted the final field testing in UTSA's drone enclosure area, a 15000 square foot and 60-foot-tall facility. An EAP225-Outdoor access point was set up to create a local wireless network between the ground robot and operator's laptop. A wooden mock bridge was set up inside of the drone cage to act as our inspection object along with construction cones to add noise to the environment. Figure 5 shows the setup and equipment for our outdoors test.

Using the developed prototype, a human inspector first create a GPS-based waypoint of the bridge structure and capture a reference image using the drone. Then, the UGV converts the GPS coordinates into a local map point and creates a global and local navigation plan to autonomously navigate to the area. The operator can monitor the UGV’s state and video feed for any issues or anomalies while the robot navigates to the target location. When the inspection target is reached, the operator directs the UGV to locate the inspection object of interest using the gaze-interface in the workspace. The UGV will wait until an inspection target area is specified by the remote operator. An image and fixation point sent to the segmentation module are passed to the SAM2 (Ravi et al. 2024) which outputs three segmentation mask predictions. These are then displayed to the user in the application’s Workspace area, where they can select a mask or reattempt the fixation process. Figure 6 shows a example of the targeted fixation segmentation. With a target surface area mask received, the UGV could begin the required inspection and data capturing process.

Figure 5. Images of the outdoor testing environment and inspection structure.

Figure 6. A segmentation mask visualization rendered in the latest user interface.

4. CONCLUSIONS

During this research project we successfully developed a gaze-directed interface for UAV-UGV coordinated site inspection. In this work, we provided an architecture overview and dataflow description of the developed human-machine interface application for multi-robot on-site component inspection. Our application allows for the integration of rapidly acquired contextual data by one robot (e.g., drone) into an inspection mission for another robot (e.g., ground robot), all while allowing a human operator to monitor and direct the inspection process and provide additional context as needed. An implementation of the application was demonstrated in a real-world scenario, showing the application’s functionality and user interface design. In future studies, we plan to run more inspection case studies to evaluate the application’s usability and impact on productivity in more realistic inspection scenarios. The current implementation serves as a functional base for use in novel inspection applications, where the software can be easily modified to extend functionality and hardware compatibility.

5. REFERENCES

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Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the financial support provided for this study by the Transportation Infrastructure Precast Innovation Center (TRANS-IPIC) through the University Transportation Center program of the US Department of Transportation, Office of the Assistant Secretary for Research and Technology (OST-R) under Grant No. 69A3552348333.